

FEATURES OF HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF SOCIALIZATION

Ismailova Gulsara Jalgasbaevna

Psychologist of the school named after I.Yusupov

Phone +998 97 2203939

Annotation. This article provides a comprehensive analysis of the peculiarities of human psychology, the processes of socialization and their relationship.

Keywords. Human psychology, socialization, thought, thinking, psyche, business acumen.

The development of modern science emphasizes the need to significantly strengthen the study of the developmental exercises of human psychology. The problem of artificial intelligence, in particular, requires the study of psychological differences in the socialization of man and the exercises of personal development.

Psychological development of a person is primarily directly related to the social center. In the science of world psychology, the interpretation of the individual as a product of the social center is accepted. It should be noted that the process of assimilation of social experience of a person, which reflects the relationship of the individual to the individual activity and the purpose for which he is engaged in spiritual activity, is characterized by personality traits, business acumen, perceptive motives.¹ In other words, entrepreneurship arises in the actions of a person who seeks to resolve the gifts in the environment.

A person's diligence helps him to choose a path for his future, to master it, to find his place in life. Monotonous living conditions have the potential to create different forms of personal activity and to create different living conditions. Thus, the notion of a person arises due to the fact that all external drivers that affect a person are enriched by social conditions, the structure of the internal educational units of business.

¹ Ш.Алланазарова, З.Матуразова. Шахстың психологиялық жағдайлары хәм өзгешеликлери. Нөкис – 2016. 39.

When a person participates in the activities of different groups in society, often they also perform various tasks, play different roles. For example, parents, children and more. It can also be humorous and amusing if it is weighty, demanding and not joining others in the line of duty, and if it is helpful and collaborative in the service.² From the above examples, one person in different situations plays opposite roles in terms of content. In some cases, a person shows the qualities that are appropriate to them in different situations, according to the circumstances, he plays the roles he has taken on in the home, in the service, in the community, in sports competitions, and so on, not against each other. The inconsistency of these human qualities, feelings, and attributes is one of the signs of a person's identity, in which contradictions, difficulties, and immature qualities are reflected in the fact that they are performed in different situations.

In Uzbekistan, the ban on the transfer of a person to a person is related to the process of building a humane, impartial, legal society, and is limited to the necessary categories, such as active participation in this social process. The development of the discipline of world psychology, as shown in the experiments of humanist scientists, shows that the psychological structure and psychological qualities of the individual form a unique, stable unity in each individual. This, in turn, allows you to strongly confirm the idea of the stability, rigidity, stereotypes of the psychological structure of the individual.

Mental conditions, gifts (feelings, desires, dreams, thoughts) are constantly changing, behavior in social groups changes depending on the role of the person in life, aging and psychological appearance of the person to some extent remains stable. This strict stability is closely connected with the stability of the set of social relations, which is formed by human interaction with the conditions of its creation, the manifestation of its physical properties. But the stability we have mentioned has a strict nature. Therefore, changes in the psychological structure of the individual have been studied in a number of studies by psychologists. These changes are the center of human creation, the implementation of which is reflected in the service, they are directly related to the social impact, the state of education. Therefore, the relatively stable and relatively variable qualities of a person consist of a composite unit consisting of the individuality and interconnectedness of human emotions.

² Ш.Алланазарова, З.Матуразова. Психологияда билиў процесслери (Оқыў-методикалық колланба). Нөкис – 2012. 32.

In short, psychological differences in the process of socialization of the individual are a measure of all social relations.

List of used literature:

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